

**CAUSES, DIAGNOSIS AND TREATMENT MEASURES OF THE
ORIGIN OF DISEASES OF PANSINUSITIS AND ALLERGIC RHINITIS
IN CHILDREN**

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Annotation

In the article we can learn about pansinusitis and allergic rhinitis in children from ENT diseases. In this case, the etiology of diseases, the main causes of their origin, the importance of diagnostics and treatment measures, the relevance of prevention are cited. Insights have been given into the importance of spying when identifying and diagnosing the causative agent.

Key words: disease, pansinusitis in children, inflammation, infection, Streptococcus, allergy, rhinitis, palpation, rhinoscopy,

In children, pansinusitis is an infectious disease characterized by inflammation of the mucous membrane inside the sinuses and lasts up to 4 weeks. This is a very common disease in children and adults. It can occur as a result of a viral or bacterial infection. In the case of the Virus, no special treatment is required, while bacterial infection is more severe and requires drug therapy. Medicines are strictly prescribed by a doctor.

In the clinical picture of the disease, traumatic damage to the middle and upper third of the skull is accompanied by the destruction of the bone structures of the sinuses and nasal septum, as a result of which the excretory pathways are clogged. When foreign objects enter the sinus, the development of similar signs is noted. The development of acute inflammation of the accessory sinuses is associated with acute respiratory infections, the causative agents of which are

respiratory syncytial infection, adenoviruses, parvoviruses. In the chronic variant of the course, bacterial flora is often a causative agent: staphylococci, beta-hemolytic Streptococci, Pneumococci.

Pain is often localized in the nose, superciliary zone, orbits, occiput, central part of the head. During palpation, painful sensations increase, swelling of soft tissues is observed in the projection of the sinuses. Headaches are caused by the spread of the inflammatory process to the membranes of the brain. Headaches do not have a pronounced localization, are exacerbated by sharp movements of the head and physical exertion. The patient complains about the difficulty in nasal breathing, which occurs against the background of obstruction of the sinus outlet openings and swelling of the mucous membrane. As a result of atrophy of the nasal mucosa, the patient's sensitivity to odors decreases or anosmia appears.

Diagnosis of pansinusitis in children is based on a set of complaints analysis, physical examination data, laboratory and instrumental studies. To confirm the diagnosis, anterior and posterior rhinoscopy, diagnostic puncture, radiography and ultrasound examination, computed tomography of the paranasal sinuses and magnetic resonance imaging are used. Etiotropic therapy with a mild course consists in choosing the right antibiotic therapy if the bacteria are the causative agent of the disease. Interferons, synthetic nucleosides are used for viral infection, and fungicides are used for fungal etiology of the disease. Symptomatic therapy is necessary to alleviate the general condition and prevent side effects of etiotropic treatment. To relieve pain, non - steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs can be used, to relieve swelling-antihistamines and glucocorticoid inflammation. To stabilize the microflora, the intake of probiotics and prebiotics is indicated.

Allergic rhinitis (hay fever) is an inflammation of the nasal mucosa caused by allergens. It was first described by John Bostock in 1819. This English doctor suggested that the cause of the disease was somehow related to hay, since the symptoms of the disease appeared when the patient came into contact.

What exactly caused allergic rhinitis was determined by another English doctor, David Blakely, 54 years after the description of the disease. It has been proven that the reason for this is the pollen of some plants. The list of such plants includes trees (Poplar, alder, Maple, etc.), cereals (oats, barley, wheat, etc.), weeds (Wormwood, herbs, etc.), fungi (their spores are allergens). In addition, it turned out that ordinary household dust can also cause this disease. In addition, some patients develop an allergic reaction from several types of pollen or pets, cats, dogs.

Not all people suffer from allergic rhinitis. Doctors note a genetic predisposition to this disease. Other factors (poor environmental conditions, removal of the tonsils) only provoke attacks, but not the cause. People with a genetic predisposition may develop allergies to almost any substance.

Treatment of allergic rhinitis in children is based on two main principles:

1. Stop contact with the Allergen.
2. The use of drugs that prevent the development of an allergic reaction. To stop the contact of the allergen with the mucous membrane, the nasal cavity is washed with special solutions (saline, Aqua Maris, etc.).

The use of correctly selected drugs has a quick and long-term effect. The drugs used in this case are divided into several groups:

1. Local vasoconstrictor drugs. These are solutions for instillation into the nose (naphthysine, galazoline, sanorin rhinoxyl, sodium chlorine solution, etc.). These drugs are used for first aid, as they relieve swelling of the mucous membrane and restore nasal breathing in a matter of seconds. However, their effect is short-lived.

2. Antihistamines. These substances block the action of free histamine, which causes an immediate reaction. They act more slowly than vasoconstrictor agents, but longer.

Topical glucocorticosteroid drugs. If the drugs of the two previous groups are not effective enough, they are used. The course of choice and treatment of drugs is determined by the allergist, who chooses the most effective treatment regimen for each patient. Immunotherapy should be considered for patients with moderate to severe chronic allergic rhinitis who do not respond to the usual procedures. Targeted immunoterepia is the only treatment that changes the natural course of allergic rhinitis, preventing exacerbation. The omalizumab anti-immunoglobulin E antibody is shown to be effective in reducing nasal symptoms and improving quality of life in patients with allergic rhinitis.

In conclusion, evaluating the causes of the origin of diseases, it is important that we identify the body's response to external influences and improve unfavorable living conditions and, most importantly, follow a healthy lifestyle, serve to reduce the likelihood of contracting the disease. In addition, we need to carry out preventive explanatory work on our patients, organize diet tables in allergy-prone patients.

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